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THE CONCEPT OF DISCOURSE, ITS INTONATION AND FUNCTIONS IN A NEW PARADIGM IN LINGUISTICS

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Abstract

The article deals with the concept of discourse from a new paradigm point of view in linguistics. It considers discourse as a unit of language which is meant to be longer and larger than a sentence. The article also informs about some origin of the term.

It reports that the concept of "discourse", which entered linguistic circulation in the 1950s. This concept, which consists of several utterances and has a single content from a structural point of view, later led to the emergence of discourse theory, and text-discourse relations became a hot topic of discussion in linguistics. The results of discussions and research on text and discourse issues were reflected in the works of foreign (M. Halliday, V. Dijk, N. Enkvist, T. Givon), Russian (I.R. Galperin, T.M. Nikolaeva, Z.Y. Turayeva, A. Kibrik, etc.) and Azerbaijani (K.M. Abdullayev, A.A. Abdullayev, A.Y. Mammadov, M.T. Gayibova, F.Y. Veysalli, and M.Y. Mammadov,) linguists. Recent studies show that this concept, initially considered as a social practice, has become a complex concept in modern linguistics with multicomponent, multifaceted and wide-ranging content. Recent studies on discourse research show that this concept in the process of verbal communication is a process that includes a number of components, including social context; specific situation, as well as psychological, sociological, linguistic and cultural phenomena.

Keywords: discourse, text, analysis, context, situation

Main Part

Discourse is considered to be a unit of language that is longer and larger than a sentence in linguistics.

The term includes two words in Latin: the prefix *dis-* and the verb *currere*. *Dis-* means "away" (beyond); *currere* means "to run". In accordance with these meanings, discourse is often explained as "to run away", that is, discourse covers the course of conversations. The study of discourse is the analysis of the use of spoken or written language in a social context.

The concept of "discourse" in linguistics is known to have entered linguistic circulation in the early 1950s with the publication of Z. Harris's article [1, p. 474]. Z. Harris approaches this concept as a unit outside the sentence, that is, larger than the sentence in that article. Starting from the late 1970s and early 1980s, along with this term, the term "text" began to be widely used in linguistics. Some linguists preferred to use the term discourse, while others preferred to use the term text. Thus, the term discourse began to be used in English-language sources, and the term text in German, Russian and Azerbaijani sources (V. Dressler, 1978; Galperin, 1981, K. Abdullayev, 1999, etc.).

As is known, the sentence was considered to be the unit of the syntactic level until the early 1980s in linguistics. However, research shows that the final unit of the syntactic level is not limited to the sentence. In this regard, K. Abdullayev's ideas are needed to be paid attention to, and they are interesting. According to this linguist, researchers approached the syntactic unit, which consists of a sentence and a union of several sentences from the same position in terms of structure. Thus, a paradoxical situation was created. According to

the scientist, the shortcomings in syntactic theory gave a special impetus to the creation of such a field as text linguistics [2, p. 178]. Recent research conducted in the field of text linguistics shows that the sentence is not the final unit in the syntactic space. Thus, at the syntactic level, after the sentence, there are micro- and macro-texts, which are also constructed in accordance with the structural model of the sentence [2, p. 178]. It is known that the concept of "text" is a Latin word, meaning connection, union. In other words, this term refers to the connection of various phenomena and sentences that are their means of grammatical expression, which have internal structural connections, and the semantic unity of this connection. Thus, on the one hand, this concept is used to define an utterance consisting of a connected sequence of several sentences to express the speaker's idea. On the other hand, the term text refers to the names of prose works (story, novel, etc.). At the same time, some linguists understand the text as a segment of speech, oral and written, of any length, forming a whole, while others view the text in close connection with the context, and still others approach the text from a broader perspective - as a syntactic unit that includes linguistic aspects (pragmatic, lexical, grammatical, stylistic, logical, etc.) [3, p. 18].

It should be noted that in linguistic sources, especially in dictionaries of linguistic terms and encyclopedias, various explanations are found regarding the explanation of the concept of "text". O.S. Akhmanova explains the concept of "text" as a) an approximate collection of utterances presented in the form of a written text selected for analysis, a tape recorder competition, etc.; b) the entire sum, collection of a speech work

created by a collective of speakers of a specific language [4, p. 209].

Expressing his attitude to the meanings explained as text in O. Akhmanova's dictionary, A. Mammadov notes that the meanings given as an explanation of the text are quite complex and ambiguous in them [5, p. 17].

This concept is explained as the intention of the speaker or writer in spoken or written form; the verbal expression of the purpose; the form of expression of activity in language for the purpose of communication in the encyclopedia of linguistics [6, p. 293]. As for the content of the concept of discourse, here too there are different approaches. Thus, researchers explain this concept as "speech carried out in the process of communication", "the process of conversation in action", "a piece of related speech" [7, p. 40].

The term "discourse" is explained as the main concept in American-English linguistics that denotes various aspects of the text, the text spoken in a coherent conversation in another linguistic source [8, p. 220].

A.Y. Mammadov considers discourse as a phenomenon formed by the intersection of cognitive and communicative processes, and he notes the differences between text and discourse according to the following parameters: while the text can be studied in its entirety as a ready-made reality, discourse should be studied as a process of creating texts with its own specific characteristics [7, p. 41].

The research conducted shows that the difference between text and discourse is that the text is understood as a structural model consisting of a number of units and having coherence, completeness and internal structural manifestations. Text as a medium is studied and considered more as abstract formal constructions, while discourse is studied and considered from the point of view of intellectual-mental processes and in relation to extralinguistic factors.

The formation of discourse, that is, the selection of language units, the finding of coherence between them, and the formation and form of discourse in accordance with the intention of the speaker or writer, is of a subjective nature. In other words, the formation and structure of discourse depends on the speaker's intention, purpose, social and communicative situation, spatial and temporal components, the intellect of the discourse participants, their worldview, and the availability of knowledge of the content of the topic.

R. Nordquist writes that discourse studies concern the form and function of language in speech beyond small grammatical units such as phonemes and morphemes [9, p. 12].

T. van Dijk is also known as one of the discourse researchers. He connects discourse with thought, that is, he writes that discourse is related to human thought. This field of research, which he was largely responsible for developing, involves the meaning created in speech by larger linguistic units, including lexemes, syntax, and context.

A. Mammadov and M. Mammadov present discourse as a coherent piece of speech. They write: "Discourse is a coherent piece of speech. However, if it is compared with the text, that its being a coherent piece

of speech does not distinguish it from the text" [10, p.22].

N. Enkvist also writes that discourse has its own characteristics: "Discourse is considered to be as part of a situation" [11, p. 369].

Discourse can sometimes reflect a word, a combination, or even a paragraph. For example, N. Enkvist's famous example: No smoking! - this piece of language is discourse when it is hung on the wall in writing. Thus, in writing, it already creates a certain situational context and is transformed into discourse.

Or "Stop!" - this is also a discourse. Alternatively, a piece of discourse can consist of hundreds of thousands of words, as in some novels.

N. Enkvist also writes that discourse is perceived as a synthesis of the text with its existing context in social life. The text acquires meaning in context. In this regard, L. Wintgenstein writes: "The context is used by the sender of the text for certain purposes, under certain conditions and in a certain sense". T. van Dijk writes: "The context includes those participating in the communication and their role, purpose, intention, general background knowledge" [12, p.32].

F. Henry and K. Tator present discourse as following: "Discourse is the social use of language to convey broad historical meanings. It is language determined by the social conditions of its use, by whom and in what circumstances it is used. Language can never be "neutral" because it connects the personal and social worlds" [13, p. 11].

Azerbaijani linguist F. Veysalli emphasizes the role of context in the use of discourse. He writes that the study of discourse is entirely context-dependent, since discourse can also encompass situational knowledge that occurs outside of speech. Often, a person cannot extrapolate meaning from a mere verbal exchange, because many semantic factors are involved in real communication [14, p. 32].

M. Bloor and T. Bloor also share this opinion. They write: "The study of discourse... can encompass issues such as context, background information, or shared knowledge between speaker and listener" [15, p. 13].

Discourse can be used to refer to specific contexts of language use, and in this sense it is similar to units such as genre or text type. For example, we can conceptualize political discourse (language used in political contexts) or media discourse (language used in the media).

In addition, some writers conceive of discourse as related to specific topics, such as ecological discourse or colonial discourse. Such labels sometimes require a specific attitude to the topic. In this regard, M. Foucault defines discourse in a more ideological sense as "practices that systematically shape the objects they speak of"... [16, p. 850].

Within the social sciences, discourse is primarily used to describe the verbal accounts of individuals. In particular, discourse is used to describe meaning for those interested in language and speech, and to analyze what people do with their speech. This approach examines the language used to describe aspects of the world and is adopted by those who use a sociological perspective.

Discourse is a collaborative activity that requires the active participation of two or more people and depends on the lives, knowledge, and communication conditions of the two or more people.

Discourse involves more than just the message between the sender and receiver of information.

It should be noted that the organization of discourse is organized with the help of language tools at all levels. These language tools are observed not only in the function of processing events within time and space, but also in the thematic development that ensures their coherence in the discourse as a whole.

Kh. Gojayeva, S. Mustafayeva highlight the role of intonation in the study of discourse.

Kh. Gojayeva writes: "The analysis of the relationship of the components of the discourse structure to the prosodic components of intonation shows that there is a structural-functional correspondence, dependence, and correlation between the content of each component of the discourse structure and the prosodic components that implement and realize the functions of intonation in the expression plan" [17, p. 22].

S. Mustafayeva analyzes discourse from the point of view of intonation and concludes that discourse is primarily related to the moment of conversation and that intonation plays an important role in its (discourse) articulation, and the syntagm is taken as the unit of this articulation [18, p. 20].

Thus, our conclusion is that discourse is a larger language unit than a sentence.

Discourse can be composed of a word, a sentence, and even a paragraph.

The formation of discourse is precisely related to the moment of speech, context, and situation.

Discourse is also considered as a verbal speech-thought activity that combines linguistic and extralinguistic components.

Communicative acts exist in discourse and they shape discourse. The study of language and linguistic phenomena at the intersection of cognition and communication is the most adequate method of investigation.

Intonation plays an important role in discourse analysis and should be understood in a broad sense. Intonation in discourse analysis is a phonological device with the help of which individual words can transform information into independent units, depending on the context and situation.

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